

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

DATA ANALYSIS OF ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING AT THE MUNICIPAL LEVEL

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Abstract

An information technology was developed that will allow to analyze environmental monitoring data at the municipal level. A dictionary of the situation attributes was created, a knowledge base was constructed, and a matrix was developed that includes fuzzy rules for recognizing situations, a compatibility matrix of situations, and a decision-making matrix. The knowledge base and a decision-making mechanism using fuzzy logic are part of the environmental monitoring information technology. A fuzzy model has been developed to identify situations, which allows updating the knowledge base and generating messages and recommendations for correcting environmental conditions, presenting management decisions. An algorithm has been developed for analyzing the situation with incomplete data received from various points in the locality to correct the knowledge base in case a known critical or abnormal situation is detected, the values of which differ from those existing in the knowledge base. The technology is aimed at improving the efficiency and accuracy of collecting, processing, and visualizing information on air quality, which is an important component of ensuring environmental safety in urban areas. The implementation of this technology will contribute to improving environmental safety at the municipal level and help address environmental pollution problems arising from human activities.

Keywords: environmental monitoring, information technology, municipalities

Introduction

The relevance of this work is determined by the importance of the environmental pollution issue and its impact on the quality of life of local populations and the state of the environment. In modern conditions, environmental issues are becoming increasingly relevant due to industrialization, emissions from transportation, technological accidents, and careless use of natural resources.

Municipal governance is a key link in responding to environmental problems. Ensuring the safety and health of citizens, preserving natural reserves and ecosystems, controlling air and water pollution levels - all these aspects require systematic monitoring and analysis of large amounts of data. Information technologies provide the opportunity to effectively analyze large volumes of information and draw important conclusions from it.

Environmental monitoring at the municipal level is a systematic process of collecting, analyzing, and evaluating information about the state of the environment (air, water, soil, biodiversity, etc.) within the municipality (city, district, village) to ensure its environmental safety and sustainable development. The main aspects of environmental monitoring at the municipal level include:

Data collection and analysis: continuous collection of data on the state of the environment, such as air and water pollution levels, soil quality, noise levels, emissions of pollutants, etc. These data are then analyzed to identify changes and trends.

Polluters monitoring: tracking the activities of enterprises and other potential environmental polluters. Checks are conducted to ensure compliance with environmental standards and regulations.

Health risks assessment: studying the impact of pollution on public health. Recommendations are developed for measures to reduce this impact.

Ecosystem monitoring: studying the state of natural ecosystems within the municipality, including diagnosing the impact of anthropogenic factors on biodiversity.

Public information and community participation: information about the state of the environment and monitoring results should be accessible to the public. The community can participate in decision-making regarding environmental protection measures.

Emergency response system: developing a system to respond to environmental emergencies, such as accidents at enterprises or natural disasters.

Sustainable development strategy: monitoring helps develop sustainable development strategies for the municipality, taking into account environmental aspects.

Reporting and management: monitoring results are used to make decisions by government authorities and develop environmental protection policies.

Municipal environmental monitoring plays a crucial role in ensuring environmental quality and public health at the local level. It helps identify problems, respond to them, and develop strategies for sustainable municipality development.

The application of information technologies in environmental monitoring at the municipal level enables rapid and accurate analysis of air quality data, water pollution levels, and the impact of anthropogenic factors on the environment. This allows for prompt responses to environmental threats and the development of effective measures for prevention and reduction.

Furthermore, information technologies facilitate interaction between government structures, research institutions, and the public in implementing measures to preserve the environment. Ensuring data openness, creating virtual platforms for information exchange and cooperation - all these aspects become available thanks to information technologies.

Thus, studying and implementing information technologies in the field of environmental monitoring at the municipal level is of great importance for the development of a sustainable, eco-friendly environment, improving the quality of life of the population, and ensuring the environmental safety of local communities.

Methodology

Various methods and approaches are used for researching and developing an information technology for analyzing environmental monitoring data at the municipal level, including methods of mathematical modeling, cluster and factor analysis, probabilistic models, and methods of statistical processing of experimental results.

These methods allow for the creation of an information technology that will ensure effective analysis of environmental monitoring data at the municipal level and contribute to making informed decisions to preserve the environment and improve the quality of life for citizens.

At the state level, air quality monitoring is carried out solely by the State Hydro Meteorological Service [1]. Therefore, municipalities (especially those in heavily industrialized cities) are left alone in solving the tasks of air quality control. Using the example of the technologically loaded urban system of Kremenchuk city, the components of the existing air quality monitoring system were analyzed, and a list of components to be developed as ways of improvement to ensure the effective operation of a comprehensive monitoring system was substantiated.

During the research, data from the Central Geophysical Observatory named after Boris Sreznevsky [3], the State Administration, and the Ministry of Ecology [8] were used.

Main Part

Today, one of the main environmental problems in Ukraine is significant pollution of the natural environment in large cities and industrial areas. The state environmental monitoring system, which was created to monitor the state of all components of the natural environment and support decision-making to ensure environmental safety and minimal risk to the health of the population in urbanized areas, unfortunately, is inefficient and has significant problems and drawbacks [6, 7].

In the work [1], it is noted that at the state level, air quality monitoring is carried out solely by the State Hydro Meteorological Service. Therefore, municipalities (especially those in heavily industrialized cities) are left alone in solving the tasks of air quality control. Using the example of the technologically loaded urban system of Kremenchuk city, the components of the existing air quality monitoring system were analyzed, and a list of components to be developed as ways of improvement to ensure the effective operation of a comprehensive monitoring system was substantiated.

During the analysis of voluminous data, tasks related to identifying hidden connections and predicting future events, as well as identifying possible deviations, can be qualitatively considered. By studying such data, it is possible to reveal the connections between events and their causes. However, there are certain uncertainties associated with this data: uncertainty of values arising from the imperfection of measuring devices, which may contain errors; time uncertainties that may arise due to possible delays in information about events; spatial uncertainties caused by the inaccuracy of event geolocation. By applying data clustering methods and creating associative rules, special methods for processing and analyzing spatio-temporal data under uncertainty conditions can be developed for use in regional monitoring and environmental safety management systems.

To achieve the main goal of the study, namely, to increase the efficiency of air quality monitoring, which includes assessing monitoring data, by creating an information technology to ensure environmental safety in highly urbanized areas at the municipal level, a special information technology for analyzing environmental monitoring data has been developed. This technology is presented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 – Information Technology for Analyzing Environmental Monitoring Data

One approach to accounting for uncertainty in forming associative rules is the creation of fuzzy associative rules in the form: if $x = Z$, then $y = R$. Where Z , R are parameters of the environment, x , y are representations of Z and R , respectively, in the form of fuzzy sets. Based on such fuzzy rules, a knowledge base was formed.

The input flow for the information technology consists of samples of atmospheric air from various research stations, which are located in a certain way near emission sources – city enterprises and residential sectors. The obtained samples of atmospheric air are pre-processed in the "Atmospheric Air Samples Analysis" block. This is necessary to exclude inadequate measurement results, i.e., gross errors, and to prepare data for entry into the system database. Based on the obtained data, risk values for each component of the environment in the urban ecosystem territory are calculated. After calculating the risk value for each component of the urban ecosystem, data processing and development of recommendations for ecosystem management take place. Developed models and algorithms for identifying emission sources act as control signals for this process. Reports and management recommendations necessary for ensuring environmental safety of the urban ecosystem territory in a given location are obtained at the output. Adequate interpretation of recommendations and reports is required at this step.

In Figure 1, the controlling influence on the process "Data Processing and Development of Management Recommendations" is the emission source identification algorithm, the steps of which are as follows.

Step 1. For each control point CP_i , according to the current wind direction DW_k , a list of table zones from the k -th emission spectra ES_{ik} is selected, and, through marker substances MS_j , the set of actual technological processes TP_j is determined. The more accurately the marker substances MS_j was selected, the more accurate the identification of emission sources SE_p will be.

Step 2. The identified technological processes TP_j are projected onto the emission sources SE_p through the TS matrix "technological processes-emission sources".

Step 3. Identified at step 2 emission sources SE_p are recorded in the i -th row of the AS matrix (table 1) in the form of "1" entries in the p -th columns. The AS matrix is intended for integrating the results of emission source identification for all objects in the industrial node.

Step 4. Formation of an updated list of control points. According to the current wind direction DW_k , those control points CP_i that contain identified emission sources from the downwind side relative to the location of the residential area are selected for processing. The list (amount) of updated control points is denoted as N_k .

Table 1

The Matrix of AS Integration of Source Identification Results

AS:	SE_p				
	1	0	1	0	1
CP_i	0	1	0	1	0
	0	1	1	1	0
	1	0	1	0	1

Step 5. After filling in all rows in the AS matrix, for each p-th column, the disjunction is calculated:

$$D_p = \bigcup_{i=1}^{N_k} as_{ip} \quad (1)$$

and a list of identified emission sources is formed.

It is worth noting that the conditional line of placement of control points should pass along the boundary of the industrial node and the residential zone. Each control point should be located so as to be on the downwind side of the industrial node for one of the wind directions from the previously determined significant wind rose sector.

To reduce the list of identified emission sources, additional (specific) criteria can be applied: the operation mode of each object of the industrial node and the current stage of each technological process, if the process is periodic.

To determine the control sectors and their characteristics, it is possible to divide the map of the conditional industrial node into a set of control sectors CS as follows:

1. For each wind direction, we build a perpendicular axis passing through the center of the industrial node and find the working segment that connects the extreme points of the industrial node on this axis. Thus, we determine the width of sector S_k , according to the given wind direction DW_k .

2. Sector S_k is divided into K subsectors PS_{kh} , ($h=1...K$).

3. The obtained sectors will have a set of intersections: $RS_{k-1} = S_k \times S_{k-1}$, $RS_{k+1} = S_k \times S_{k+1}$.

Thus, one of the previously tentatively determined points of location of control stations (observation posts) should be located in the area of intersection of three adjacent sectors on the downwind side of the industrial node for one of the wind directions from the defined wind rose sector. This location point is relevant for justifying practical recommendations regarding the placement of a stationary observation post (control stations). However, this location can also be used during episodic observations in the vicinity of the industrial node using mobile monitoring stations.

4. In each subsector PS_{kh} , which does not intersect with others, an additional control point can be installed, both stationary and mobile.

5. Determine the set of parameters X - characteristics of control sectors that should be considered when choosing the location of the mobile monitoring point. Among the characteristics, the following should be taken into account:

wind direction during the period of maximum appeals x_1 ;

frequency of appeals (number per time unit) – x_2 ;
reliability of appeals within this sector – x_3 .

Thus, a description of characteristics has been formed to determine the locations of control stations. This will allow determining the location of stationary observation posts to obtain integrated data on the state of air pollution formed within the residential areas on the downwind side of this industrial node. To select relevant locations for the placement of mobile monitoring

stations, it is necessary to develop a selection model taking into account additional conditions.

To describe the conceptual model of identification and control of emission sources, a knowledge base was created in the form of a matrix for the identification and control of emission sources.

The prevailing wind directions (x_{25}) for the city of Kremenchuk are: during the heating period East – 16.5%, Southeast – 14.8%, Southwest – 12.8%, West – 17.3%; annual average values: East – 15.8%, West – 17.8%, Northwest – 13.8%. For the following wind directions, the repeatability is close to 12.5%: South – 12.4% during the heating period and Southeast – 12.0% according to the annual wind rose [5].

Taking into account the geographical features of the location of the group of industrial enterprises in Kremenchuk, it can be concluded that the significant wind directions influencing the residential development are: North, Northeast, East. The worst conditions contributing to the formation of the highest ground-level concentrations in pollution zones due to reduced efficiency of pollutant dispersion occur at average wind speeds below 2 m/s.

The following wind speed levels were adopted: "low wind speed": from 0 to 1 m/s; "medium wind speed": from 1 to 2 m/s; and "high wind speed": 2 m/s and above. The set of observations is divided into three groups according to wind speed levels.

There is a dependence of pollutants content in the air on weather conditions: maximum concentrations are usually observed during warm calm weather, while they sharply decrease during prolonged storms, strong winds, and after precipitation.

To recognize the degree of criticality of environmental situations, the following stages were performed:

1. The list of marker substances (substances for which concentration should be monitored primarily) was determined, the concentration of which is attributed to the main indicators of the situation from the set $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$: x_1 – sulfur(IV) oxide (SO₂); x_2 – nitrogen(IV) oxide (NO).

2. The list of substances to be monitored at a specific control point was determined (the concentrations of such substances are attributed to the main indicators of the situation from the set): x_3 – carbon(II) oxide (CO); x_4 – nitrogen(II) oxide (NO); x_5 – hydrogen sulfide; x_6 – formaldehyde; x_7 – methane; x_8 – methyl mercaptan; x_9 – ammonia; x_{10} – total hydrocarbons; x_{11} – phenol; x_{12} – dust.

Thus, a dictionary of factors – indicators of situations (examples) has been formed, which includes concentrations of substances: carbon(II) oxide (CO), nitrogen(II) oxide (NO), nitrogen(IV) oxide (NO₂), sulfur(IV) oxide (SO₂), hydrogen sulfide, formaldehyde, methane, methyl mercaptan, ammonia, total hydrocarbons, dust (solid sedimented particles undifferentiated by composition).

Figure 2 shows the structure of the knowledge base for 2020-2021. Cells with incomplete data are highlighted in pink: the cell from the respective control point blinks, the value is not constant, not defined, then a dash is placed in its place in the sample. The absence of values may also be due to the fact that the devices

did not record readings for various reasons. That is, the samples contain "anomalous" values and data gaps that cannot be restored by traditional methods, so some cells in Figure 2 are marked with a dash «-».

№	Input variables																								
	x1	x2	x3	x4	x5	x6	x7	x8	x9	x10	x11	x12	x13	x14	x15	x16	x17	x18	x19	x20	x21	x22	x23	x24	x25
1	0,39	0,27	8	0,46	0,036	0,13	0,001	0,003	0,024	0,006	0,003	5	8,39	0,85	0,426	0,52	0,391	0,393	0,414	0,66	0,66	8,024	8,27	5	225
2	0,38	0,26	7,619	0,46	0,036	0,13	0,0012	0,003	0,024	0,006	0,0031	4,6667	7,999	0,84	0,416	0,51	0,381	0,383	0,404	0,64	0,64	7,643	7,879	5	225
3	0,38	0,25	7,429	0,46	-	0,13	0,0012	0,003	0,024	0,006	0,0031	4,6667	7,809	0,84	0,38	0,51	0,381	0,383	0,404	0,62	0,63	7,453	7,679	5	45
4	0,37	0,25	7,429	0,46	0,035	0,13	0,0012	0,003	0,024	0,006	0,0031	4,3333	7,799	0,83	0,405	0,5	0,371	0,373	0,394	0,62	0,62	7,453	7,679	5	45
5	0,37	0,24	7,238	0,46	0,035	0,13	-	0,0035	0,024	0,005	0,0031	4,3333	7,608	0,83	0,405	0,5	0,37	0,374	0,394	0,62	0,61	7,262	7,478	4,37	50
6	0,37	0,24	7,238	0,46	0,035	0,13	0,0014	0,0037	0,027	0,005	0,0031	4,3333	7,608	0,83	0,405	0,5	-	0,374	0,397	0,62	0,61	7,265	7,478	4,1	39
7	0,37	0,23	7,048	0,45	0,035	0,13	0,0014	0,0037	0,027	0,005	0,29	4,3333	7,418	0,82	0,405	0,5	0,371	0,374	0,397	0,61	0,6	7,075	7,278	4,3	216
8	0,37	0,23	68,57	0,45	0,035	0,13	0,0014	0,037	0,027	0,005	0,29	4,3333	68,94	0,82	0,405	0,5	0,371	0,407	0,397	0,61	0,6	68,6	68,8	4,3	233
9	0,37	0,22	6,667	0,45	0,035	0,15	0,0014	0,0035	0,027	0,005	0,29	4,3333	7,037	0,82	0,405	0,52	0,371	0,374	0,397	0,61	0,59	6,694	6,887	4,4	218
10	0,37	0,22	6,667	-	0,035	0,15	0,0014	0,003	0,031	0,005	0,29	-	7,037	0,37	0,37	0,52	0,371	0,373	0,401	0,6	0,59	6,698	6,887	4,3	231
11	0,36	0,22	6,667	0,47	0,035	0,15	0,0014	0,0029	0,031	0,065	0,29	4	7,027	0,83	0,395	0,51	0,361	0,363	0,391	0,6	0,58	6,698	6,887	4,37	225
12	0,36	0,21	6,667	0,47	0,035	0,15	0,0014	0,0029	0,031	0,065	0,29	4	7,027	0,83	0,395	0,51	0,361	0,363	0,391	-	0,57	6,698	6,877	4,9	41
13	0,36	0,21	6,667	0,47	0,035	0,15	0,0014	0,0029	-	0,065	0,031	4	7,027	0,83	0,395	0,51	0,361	0,363	0,36	0,59	0,57	6,004	6,877	5,1	49
14	0,35	0,21	6,667	0,47	0,035	0,15	0,015	0,0029	0,03	0,065	0,031	4	7,017	0,82	0,385	0,5	0,365	0,353	0,38	0,59	0,56	6,697	6,877	5	54
15	0,35	0,2	6,476	0,47	0,034	0,15	0,015	0,0029	0,03	0,065	0,031	4	6,826	0,82	0,384	0,5	0,365	0,353	0,38	0,59	0,55	6,506	6,676	5,2	35
16	0,35	0,2	6,476	0,47	0,034	0,15	0,015	0,0029	0,029	0,065	0,031	4	6,826	0,82	0,384	0,5	0,365	0,353	0,379	0,58	0,55	6,505	6,676	4,9	45
17	0,35	0,2	6,286	0,49	0,034	0,15	0,015	0,003	0,029	0,007	0,031	4	6,636	0,84	-	0,5	0,365	0,353	0,379	0,58	0,55	-	6,486	4,7	51
18	0,35	0,2	6,286	0,49	0,034	0,15	0,015	0,0031	0,029	0,007	0,003	4	6,636	0,84	0,384	0,5	0,365	0,353	0,379	0,58	0,55	6,315	6,486	4,75	38
19	0,35	0,2	6,286	0,49	0,034	0,18	0,015	0,0031	0,029	0,007	0,003	4	6,636	0,84	0,384	0,53	0,365	0,353	0,379	0,58	0,55	6,315	6,486	4,8	230
20	0,35	0,2	6,286	0,49	-	0,18	0,013	0,0031	0,029	0,007	0,003	4	6,636	0,84	0,35	0,53	0,363	0,353	0,379	0,58	0,55	6,315	6,486	5	219
21	0,35	0,2	6,095	0,49	0,037	0,18	0,013	0,032	0,029	0,007	0,003	4	6,445	0,84	0,387	0,53	0,363	0,382	0,379	0,58	0,55	6,124	-	5,14	53
22	0,34	0,2	6,095	0,49	0,037	0,18	0,013	0,032	0,029	0,006	0,032	4	6,435	0,83	0,377	-	0,353	0,372	0,369	0,56	0,54	6,124	6,295	5	36

Figure 2 – Structure of Knowledge Base for 2020-2021

3. Concentrations of pollutants were normalized in the range $\langle 0 \div 1 \rangle$ according to established standards of MPC (maximum permissible concentration) of measured concentration values of pollutants.

4. Codes of combinations of concentrations of pollutant groups were determined (these combinations are also indicators of the situation).

5. Additional factors (indicators) - x_{24} , x_{25} , which influence the integral assessment of the degree of air pollution, were determined: critical wind speeds and directions. Wind speed «LOW»: 0–2 m/s, «MEDIUM»: 2–5 m/s, «HIGH»: above 5 m/s.

6. An expert survey was conducted to determine fuzzy ranges characterizing critical, pre-critical, and normal concentration values of each marker substance: $T_1 = \langle \text{Normal} \rangle$, $T_2 = \langle \text{Pre-critical} \rangle$, $T_3 = \langle \text{Critical} \rangle$. Verbal assessments were obtained for the defined terms Z_i . If the ratio of the actual concentration to the established norm exceeds $\langle 1 \rangle$, then the situation is assessed as critical (term $T_3 = \langle \text{Critical} \rangle$), and the value is normalized to $\langle 1 \rangle$. As a result, a scale of linguistic variables was obtained (Table 2).

Table 2

Situation characteristics	Scale of linguistic variables		
	Value of the characteristic corresponding to the term		
	«Normal»	«Pre-critical»	«Critical»
x1	0 – 0,2	0,1 – 0,7	0,6 – 1,0
x2	0 – 0,25	0,15 – 0,75	0,7 – 1,0
x3	0 – 0,5	0,4 – 0,7	0,6 – 1,0
x4	0 – 0,2	0,15 – 0,75	0,6 – 1,0
x5	0 – 0,1	0,05 – 0,5	0,4 – 1,0
x6	0 – 0,21	0,17 – 0,5	0,4 – 1,0
x7	0 – 0,2	0,1 – 0,4	0,35 – 1,0
x8	0 – 0,4	0,3 – 0,65	0,6 – 1,0
x9	0 – 0,35	0,3 – 0,75	0,6 – 1,0

7. Membership functions were constructed: after the expert determined the degree of membership of the parameters under study in the given fuzzy set, membership functions of fuzzy terms were constructed in the

form of trapezoids for control parameters obtained as a result of calculations.

Membership function models for fuzzy variables x_3 and x_{19} are presented in Figure 3 a), b).

the example of the technogenically loaded city of Kremenchuk.

The technology includes modern methods of data analysis based on artificial intelligence, machine learning, and geographic information systems. The implementation of this technology will contribute to the improvement of monitoring quality by enabling the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data with greater accuracy and speed. This innovative technology will not only simplify the process of data collection and processing but will also enable informed decision-making to improve the quality of atmospheric air.

Thus, the creation and implementation of an information technology for analyzing environmental monitoring data at the municipal level represent an important step towards creating an effective environmental control system, contributing to the improvement of residents' quality of life and ensuring environmental safety in urban areas.

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